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Critical Review of Common Evaluation Models for Missiological Training Programmes

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Abstracts

This study examines the crucial role of evaluation in missiological training programs, emphasizing the necessity of effective training for fulfilling the cultural and the Great Commission mandate. Despite its importance, evaluation is often neglected in missiological training. Many missiological training centres have existed for decades without a deliberate effort to evaluate the effectiveness of the programme. The study employs a comprehensive analysis of existing scholarly articles, books, and conference papers related to missiological training programs, evaluation models, and their effectiveness to arrive at this review. This critical review assesses common evaluation models applicable to missiological training, enabling trainers to select and adopt suitable frameworks. The study addresses the gap between training and competency development and highlights the importance of evaluation in assessing training outcomes, identifying areas for improvement, and enhancing the overall quality of missiological training. By examining various evaluation models, trainers and educators can select and adapt frameworks that align with their program's objectives and goals. This research aims to contribute to the development of more effective missiological training programs, ultimately strengthening the capacity of mission practitioners to engage diverse cultural contexts and fulfill the Great Commission and social responsibilities of the church.

Keywords: Missiological Training, Evaluation Models, Great Commission, Cross-Cultural Engagement, Missionary Competence

Introduction

Missiological training programme is fundamental to the fulfilment of the cultural and the Great Commission mandate of the Church. It is the means through which individuals called into missions are prepared and equipped for cross-cultural engagement and service. Without effective missiological training programmes, the missionary task of making disciples of all nations, planting culturally relevant churches among unreached peoples, and transforming the nation through the message of love and peace will be a mirage (Engel & Dyrness, 2000). The effectiveness of training is directly tied to the quality and rigor of its evaluation process. Evaluation is, however, scarcely done for missiological training programmes. For this reason, this study presents a critical review of common evaluation models that can be adopted for missiological training (Garrett, 1998). Through this, trainers can select a model that best suits their aim of evaluation and adopt it for use.

The concept of evaluation of missiological training is vital to the effectiveness and improvement of mission training programmes. Failure to do regular evaluation may be counterproductive to the standardization and up-to-date evolving of any training programme, and this can prevent the growth of any institution (Slack, 1998). Evaluation is the process through which an institution or organization assesses its performance over a period. Every training institution needs to engage in regular periodic evaluation to ascertain the worth of its programme, assess the effectiveness of the method of training, measure the impact of the output of training, determine to what extent the training achieves the set goal or purpose, appraise the strength and weaknesses of the training, and improve the entire training programme to meet with the present reality (Willis, 1998).

Missiological training is divine strategy to fulfill the mandate of the Great Commission - the Church marching order (Steffen, 2000). Missions training is responsible for equipping various harvest workforce, for instance, frontier missionaries who engage in extending the frontier of missions; mission mobilizers who awaken the Church to missions, her foremost mandate on Earth; mission pastors who lead new churches on the field or in urban cities to keep missions as the focus of the Church and motivate members to be involved in missions; mission trainers who equip those called to missions, shape their vision and guide them to understand their calling; and tentmakers who use their professions to

propagate the gospel in restricted or creative access nations are all products of mission training (Madaus & Stufflebeam, 2000). Mission training is both the initial step in engaging least reached peoples and the mark of completion of mission work among a targeted people group (Crenshaw, 2022). This assertion stands upon the fact that God's first strategy in reaching the world is to send divinely called missionaries to bear incarnational witness among various people groups of the world, and for effectiveness, these people must be trained (Fard Moradi et al., 2022). It is equally true that the work of a frontier missionary cannot be adjudged complete until indigenous leaders are raised and trained to take over from the missionary (Fitriyanti Noho et al., 2023). This, therefore, means that the extent to which the remaining task of missions will be completed largely depends on the number of competent missionaries trained and redeployed to the harvest field (Nabea1 & Wanani, 2022). Consequently, mission training stands as an important link between the Church and the remaining task of missions. Completing this task, that is, discipling all nations everywhere, among many other factors depends on the quality and effectiveness of the training received by those called into missions (Lynch, 1996).

Missiological training mostly takes place in theological institutions, Bible schools, local churches, and missionary training centres (Mathison, 2005). This training could be formal, informal, and non-formal (iEduNote, 2023). However, training alone is not sufficient to produce competent harvest workers; only effective training does (Andales, 2021). The process through which training programmes are made effective is evaluation (Neendoor, 2020). So, evaluation of missiological training is directly linked to the fulfillment of the Church's missionary mandate. The concept of evaluation is fundamental to the improvement, growth, and rapid development of mission programmes in an institution (Ferris, 1995). Scholars have created different models for the evaluation of educational programmes. The models use all or parts of training components, as well as stakeholders' opinions to evaluate a particular training programme (Gonzalez, 2023).

Concept of Training Programme Evaluation

Educational evaluation as it is known today was first developed in the USA before it spread to other parts of the world (Stufflebeam, 2003). Today, evaluation has become popular and a highly debatable

educational theme because of its distinctive nature and function used as a defining factor in the usefulness and effectiveness of educational programs in all great citadels of learning globally (Kim, 2022). Development of a training programme is not a one-time event; rather, it is an ongoing process that needs periodic evaluation to make it effective and relevant to its context and evolving circumstances around the globe (Newcomer & Wholey, 2015). Evaluation is an intrinsic part of the teaching and learning process and so should be made part of any programme development, remain in the development process, and continue after the programme development to ensure that the programme remains faithful to its training commitments, objectives, and goals (Vardaman, 2022). Monitoring and evaluation should equally be made an integral part of educational institution policy that will be factored into the planning from the outset, and trainers, who are key stakeholders in educational programmes, should be actively involved in the evaluation process and in getting timely feedback from the process using technological tools and best practices available for data gathering (Stufflebeam, 2001).

Evaluation is an intrinsic part of the learning process, which as a whole cannot be separated from teaching and learning activities; evaluation is a measuring tool or process to find out the level of success achieved by students on teaching materials or materials that have been submitted so that, with an evaluation, the objectives of learning will be seen accurately and convincingly (Zafar et al., 2021). Evaluation is defined simply as “the systematic attempt to gather information in order to make judgments or decisions” (Cahapay, 2021). In this regard, evaluation is a tool for decision-making. Another scholar defined it as “an applied inquiry process for collecting and synthesizing evidence that culminates in conclusions about the state of affairs, value, merit, worth, significance, or quality of a program, product, person, policy, proposal, or plan” (O’Connell, 2021). This definition explains evaluation as a process that seeks to gather data that reveals the true state, merits, and worth through analysis, and from which appropriate decisions can be based (Schalock, 2001a). In the context of training, varying definitions of evaluation have been given. Training evaluation has been thought to be “the process of collecting the outcomes needed to determine if training is effective” (Hakan & Seval, 2011). This definition views evaluation as what a company does to ascertain the effectiveness of the training

programme, in order to find out if the money invested has been wisely spent (Roberts, 2021). Another scholar defined training evaluation as “the systematic process of analyzing if training programs and initiatives are effective and efficient” (Kline, 2023). This scholar sees evaluation as a tool that trainers and human resource professionals use to assess if employees’ training programs align with and meet the company’s goals and objectives (Far & Karimi Moonaghi, 2023). Still, training evaluation is conceived as an attempt to obtain relevant information on the effects of a training programme (Mohebbi et al., 2011). Here, evaluation is considered an important part of the training programme for the purpose of reflection, analysis, and improvement of its effectiveness and efficiency (Booth, 2020). Programme evaluation is also considered as any procedure that brings about a critical and knowledgeable reflection on training commitments, training goals, and stewardship of resources involved in training (Pipia, 2014). A thorough and more comprehensive definition of evaluation is given as “the process of delineating, obtaining, providing, and applying descriptive and judgmental information about the merit and worth of some object’s goals, design, implementation, and outcomes to guide improvement decisions, provide accountability reports, inform institutionalization/ dissemination decisions, and improvement decisions, and understanding of the involved phenomena” (Spiegel et al., 1999).

In education, evaluation refers to the process of assessing and measuring the learning outcomes, performance, progress, and effectiveness of educational programs, courses, teachers, students, and institutions (Posavac, 2015). It's a systematic and ongoing process that involves gathering data and evidence to make informed judgments about the quality and impact of educational practices (Williamson, 2020). Evaluation plays a crucial role in improving the educational system by identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement (Thompson, 2023). It is fundamentally the process of determining the value, worth, and significance of a particular activity against set standards (Husson, 2021). In the training context, it is the application of systematic methods to address questions about programme operations and results to enhance knowledge about the underlying effectiveness and usefulness of the programme (Uche, 2022). Evaluation is also viewed as “a study designed and conducted to assist some audience to assess an object’s merit and worth” (Ibeh, 2021). “Merit” in this context

is the presence of values affirmed broadly among educators of a particular type (in this context mission trainers), and “worth”, on the other hand, is the presence of values specific to one programme and its context (Nassim et al., 2023). The “worth” is what makes a training programme distinct from others; it includes but transcends the goals of the training programme and is basically the function of the needs and expectations of the training programme’s stakeholders or constituencies such as local churches, mission agencies, and Boards, and groups and individuals that the programme serves. The “worth” also relates to how appropriate a programme is to the cultural context of the trainee and the recipient host community (Hu, 2021). Using the above definition of evaluation, programme evaluation approaches are classified into four categories: first, pseudo-evaluations (approaches that promote invalid or incomplete findings); second, is a Questions and/or Methods-Oriented approach; third, is an Improvement/Accountability approach; and fourth, is a Social Agenda/Advocacy approach (Kurtz, 2021). The primary objective of evaluating any training programme is to develop an understanding of whether it has achieved its stated objectives. Evaluations generally provide required information for decision-making, policy creation, and future programme planning (Kylan et al., 2021). For the information provided to be useful for these purposes, evaluation must be thorough, accurate, reliable, and provided on time (Hakan & Seval, 2011). With respect to the targets, educational evaluation can be divided into macro and micro evaluations, with enhancement of premeditated endeavors as the primary objective of the macro evaluation, while micro evaluations serve to assess pedagogy within the classroom setting (Lindgren, 2023).

A scholar suggested three aspects of missiological training programme that are considered necessary for evaluation exercise: training processes, the training outcomes, and the stewardship of resources (Lacy, 2022). Training processes in missions include all intentional activities and relationships by which missiological training programmes seek to shape the understanding, skills, and characters of trainees (Warju, 2016). Evaluation of the training process is done by examining each component for consistency with the programme’s training commitments and goals for stewardship of the programme’s resources (Mwanza, 2023). The training outcomes could be intended or unintended outcomes. The intended outcomes are assessed in terms of training goals and objectives,

and the exercise could be made simple where training goals are specified and objectives well defined (Zhang, 2023). The unintended outcomes assessment is similar to process evaluation. The list of unintended outcomes is first generated by trainers, students in training, alumni, churches, and mission agencies, and this list is then compared with training commitment and goals (Cummings, 2023). Programme stewardship comprises financial resources, physical resources, personnel resources, and the environment (Karam, 2023). Strategies available for programme evaluation to ascertain training effectiveness and the attainment of training goals and objectives are tests of trainees' knowledge or skills, exhibits relating to trainer or trainee portfolios or products demonstrating skills, direct inquiry methods through interviews or questionnaires, and direct observation (Amato, 2020). Of these, direct inquiry has been adjudged the most useful way to obtain information about persons and their opinions, and the only means for assessing the attainment of character development goals (Hakan & Seval, 2011). Interviews are preferred to questionnaires except when the respondents are widely dispersed geographically or the number of individuals to be questioned is relatively large (Wise, 2020). A given programme model should have four elements: namely, programme activities, anticipated outcomes, operative mechanisms, and the context (Santos, 2023).

Models of Training Programme Evaluation

A model is a “simple description of a system used for explaining how something works” (Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary of Current English, 2015). Programme evaluation model is a systematically structured tool made to improve the quality, integrity, and standards of different educational programs. Several models for evaluating training programme effectiveness have been developed and experimented by scholars and practitioners. Each of the training models has its own merits and demerits. While some fit well into educational institutions, others are adaptable to businesses and organizations; still, others cut across all fields and disciplines. The implementation of any of the models for assessment of educational programs will depend largely on the need and goal of an institution or organization, the structure of the evaluation model and its objectivity, the feasibility and cost-effectivity, the intentions of the evaluation, and the nature of the programme to be

evaluated (Stufflebeam, 2001). Depending on the meaning and perspective, educational evaluation models are categorized into objective-oriented, management-oriented, consumer-oriented, expertise-oriented, participant-oriented, and adversary-oriented evaluation models (Stufflebeam, 2001). Scholars have worked hard to summarize the key points of these models.

“The objective-oriented evaluation approach focuses on establishing goals in advance, and then on determining how far the goals have been achieved. Since the emphasis is on outcomes of training such as the effectiveness of education and student achievement, the evaluation of teaching and learning process can be overlooked. The management-oriented evaluation approach considers an evaluation to assist decision-making by providing decision makers with the necessary information. This approach permits the evaluator to assess all aspects of the programme implementations but is limited because it is difficult to be fully implemented. The consumer-oriented evaluation approach regards everything used for education as an education product, and furthermore, conducts education as a service. The focus is on the satisfaction of consumers of the education programme and can demotivate teachers and curriculum developers. The expertise-oriented evaluation approach is the oldest and most widely used model, and it uses the method of evaluating education by expert judgment. This approach can lead to irrational deliberations, since the weights of the criteria for the trivial and the important are not presented, and managerial prejudice can influence the formation of a review team. The adversary-oriented evaluation approach is able to collect the opinions of the subjects broadly by dealing with all the opposing views in one evaluation and helps shed light on the advantages and disadvantages of the education program. The participant-oriented evaluation approach takes an all-inclusive approach to humanistic issues in complex contexts and is characterized by value pluralism, and therefore can take a very different approach than other assessment approaches. There is a possibility of subjective or prejudiced interventions in the assessment, and the fact that the evaluator’s role in the assessment is excluded makes it impossible for the evaluation method to assume the role of assessment” (Culley, 2023).

The purpose of an evaluation model is to assess whether the programme fulfills the required needs, provides anticipated services, delivers the desired outcomes, achieves its goals and objectives, and is functioning in

the way it was planned (Stufflebeam, 2004). Evaluation of an educational programme intends to check the program's progress, identify merits and flaws, and acquire information. After analyzing the quality indicators of educational programs by an evaluation model, previous decisions are either maintained or modified to achieve better programme outcomes. Notable among the widely used education evaluation models for consideration are Kirkpatrick's Four-Level Model, Stufflebeam's CIPP Model, Stake's Responsive Model, Tyler's Objective Model, Outcome-Based Model, Logic Model, and Scriven's Goal Free Model (Mathison, 2005).

Kirkpatrick's Four-Level Model

This model is developed and designed by Don Kirkpatrick for educational programme evaluation and has been found to be among the most widely used methods for evaluating the effectiveness of both educational and corporate training programs (Kirkpatrick, 1994). The framework offers a comprehensive four-level strategy consisting of reaction, learning, behavior, and results to evaluate the effectiveness of any training course or programme (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006). It emphasizes assessing participants' reactions, knowledge acquisition, application of learning in practice, and the overall impact of training on desired outcomes. This model breaks down evaluation into four successive levels which build on information provided by the previous level. First, the reaction level is used to measure how trainees responded to training, and this can be gauged by allowing participants to complete a short survey or feedback form. The learning level aims at understanding what the participants learned from the training and the level of changes in trainee's knowledge and skill is measured by giving short quizzes or tests. The behavior level follows the learning level and it is to assess whether the training has resulted in positive change in behavior, that is, to know if trainees put into practice what they have learned and to what extent the trainee is effective in changing their attitude. Usually, this is assessed by asking trainees to fill a self-assessment form or by supervisor formal assessment, workplace observation, and comparing behaviors of trainees before and after training. Result is the last level which measures the outcome of the training against the expectations of the organization or the stakeholders. It is achieved by determining whether the participants have met learning

objectives through positive change in productivity, morale, quality, sales, efficiency, etc. (Kirkpatrick, 1994). The strength of this model is in its ability to simplify the complex process of evaluation; focus on the training and behavior of the trainees, and reduction of measurement demand. The limitations of this model are found in the interdependency of the components; it focuses mainly on training and participants' behavior making it non-comprehensive, failure to take into account the effect of variables; greater significance given to upper levels (behavior and outcomes) than lower levels (reaction and learning); difficulty in evaluating levels 3 and 4 and causal effects of components (Bates, 2005). Evaluators need to take into consideration these aforementioned limitations while adopting the Kirkpatrick model in evaluating higher education programs. The Kirkpatrick model can be improved by giving equal significance to all components of the training program, using a comprehensive mechanism, and modifying the model to be applicable in other programs beyond training programs (Moreau, 2017).

Context, Input, Process and Product (CIPP) Model

CIPP is an acronym of context, input, process, and product. The model is developed by Stufflebeam to evaluate training programs by considering four dimensions: context, input, process, and product. This model has been widely used to evaluate programmes, policies, and can also be used to evaluate the curriculum on a small scale (Stufflebeam, 2003). The basic framework of the model is complete; that is, the context evaluation helps formulate objectives; input evaluation helps prepare the program; process evaluation directs enforceability of a programme, and product evaluation determines the achievement of a programme. In other words, context evaluation helps to develop goals, input evaluation helps to shape proposals, process evaluation guides implementation, and product evaluation serves recycling decisions (Stufflebeam, 2001). The CIPP approach examines the alignment of the programme with contextual needs, the quality of resources and instructional methods, the implementation process, and the resulting outcomes (Madaus & Stufflebeam, 2000). Context evaluation includes assessment of the program's objectives, policies that support the vision and mission of the institution, the relevant environment, needs, opportunities, and specific problems (Fard Moradi et al., 2022); input evaluation provides information about the sources (such as student components,

infrastructure, media, teacher) that can be used to achieve programme objectives and is also used to find a problem-solving strategy, planning, and design programs; process evaluation serves to provide feedback to the individual to take responsibility for the activities of the programme or curriculum; and product evaluation measures and interprets the achievement of objectives as well as the impact of the expected and unexpected outcomes (Warju, 2016).

CIPP evaluation model produces four types of decisions at each stage of evaluation: context evaluation results in planning decisions that affect the choice of goals and objectives; input evaluation leads to structuring decisions that ensure the design of strategies and procedures are optimal to achieve the goals; process evaluation engenders implementing decisions that improve the work done by selecting the right designs, methods, and strategies; and product evaluation serves recycling decisions that establish continuity, change, or terminate the programme activities (Warju, 2016). The four stages of CIPP evaluation involve the following specific steps: recognizing the kinds of decisions to take, identifying the kinds of data needed, collection of data needed, establishing criteria for determining quality, analyzing data based on predetermined criteria, and providing needed information to decision-makers (Hakan & Seval, 2011). Among the identified strengths of CIPP models are multipurpose application, simplicity, comprehensiveness, flexibility, long history of applicability, helping in objective evaluation of the program, and focusing on all the strategies and elements of the evaluation (Engel & Dyrness, 2000; Slack, 1998; Willis, 1998). Another advantage is the possibility of evaluators using the whole CIPP model for their evaluation or just selecting one dimension of the CIPP model for use. Aside from the numerous advantages, the CIPP model has some drawbacks. The model is said to be similar to the needs assessment and may take longer time especially when the entire components are considered in the evaluation (Lee, 2023).

Responsive Evaluation Model

Among training programmes evaluation models, the responsive evaluation model has been adjudged as the most suitable for commitments and values of ministry trainers (Kim, 2022). In this approach, training evaluation is concerned with the responses of various groups of people affected by the training programme. It proceeds from a

set of assumptions which ministry trainers can endorse. Concerning responsive evaluation, the following assertions were made: “it views reality as holistic, its stance is participative, its goal is programme improvement, its interest is to learn from human responses and assessments, and its assumptions are sensitive to moral and educational values” (Stake, 1975). The responsive evaluation model, otherwise known as client-oriented approach, was developed by Robert Stake in 1983. The model is tagged client-centered evaluation because the evaluator must work with and for the support of a diverse client group such as teachers, administrators, developers, taxpayers, legislators, and financial sponsors. In the same way, those referred to as clients are so because they support, develop, administer, or directly operate the programs under study and seek or need evaluators’ counsel and advice in understanding, judging, and improving programs (Hurteau & Nadeau, 1985).

An evaluation is said to be responsive “if it orients more directly to programme activities than to programme intents; responds to audience requirements for information; and if the different value perspectives present are referred to in reporting the success and failure of the programme” (Mathison, 2005). The focus in responsive evaluation is on the primary stakeholders, gathered through conversations with these parties on an ongoing basis during the evaluation. In this model of evaluation, the evaluator is not an independent or objective assessor but plays the role of a fully subjective partner who is not just highly involved in the programme but is also interactive and provides an avenue for continued communication and feedback throughout the evaluation process (Rogers, 2000). The responsive model is thought to be a leading entry in the “relativistic school of evaluation,” which calls for a pluralistic, flexible, interactive, holistic, subjective, constructivist, and service-oriented approach (Weiss & Jacoss, 1988). In summary, responsive evaluation has the following advantages: “it allows questions to emerge during the evaluation process rather than being preformulated; it enables the evaluator to acquire a rapid understanding of the programme and to determine which issues and concerns are most important to a variety of stakeholders. It is a flexible approach that uses content-rich information to portray a programme in a way that is readily accessible to audiences” (Glatthorn, 1987). Part of the limitations of the responsive evaluation approach includes a large time commitment to the

evaluation process and the need for highly skilled evaluators, the possibility of the role of the evaluator becoming ambiguous because of high levels of interaction between evaluators and stakeholders resulting in the evaluator serving as a resource person rather than a researcher, and the flexibility of the model can also distract the researcher from the focus of the evaluation, which can result in a failure to answer specific questions (Cummings, 2023; Finney, 2019).

Outcome-based Model

In the context of programme evaluation through the outcome-based model, the word outcome is defined as benefits that accrue to programme participants in the form of achievements or changes in skill, knowledge, attitude, behavior, condition, or life status through the programme (Schalock, 2001b). Any project aimed at providing these kinds of benefits is described as having outcome goals. Outcome-based evaluation (OBE) is therefore a systemic way of assessing the extent to which a programme has achieved its intended result. It answers questions such as "What difference did the programme make?" and "How did the participant benefit from the program?" (Schalock, 2001a). It identifies observations that can credibly demonstrate change or desirable conditions. It systematically collects information about these indicators and uses that information to show the extent to which a programme achieved its goals. The outcome-based evaluation model is valuable as a planning and advocacy tool and can also help communicate the value and success of a program. Organizations need to measure outcomes to demonstrate good stewardship of resources. The main purpose of the outcome-based model is summarized as finding out the expected and actual outcomes of a program, accountability demands of the program, goals and objectives of the program, efficiency and effectiveness, functionality and the policies on which the programme runs, and the use of information and feedback to improve the programme (Schalock, 2001b). The outcome-based evaluation model takes into consideration stakeholders, promoters, and programme evaluators. During the evaluation process of a given program, the model employs four major approaches: programme evaluation, effectiveness evaluation, impact evaluation, and policy evaluation (Stufflebeam, 2001). The strength of this model lies in it being outcome-based, flexible, and comparable. It is, however, deficient because it is specific and cannot

be used for every project, narrow, quantifiable, and observable (Schalock, 2001b). The model can be improved through comprehensive modifications and generalization. The model is used for educational programs, health, and organization evaluation.

Logic Model

The logic model has been defined as “a tool that describes the theory of change underlying an intervention, product, or policy. It characterizes a project through a system of elements that include components and connections, with context being an important qualification” (Frechtling, 2007). This model, otherwise referred to as a programme model or theory of change, is “a planning tool and visual representation of the resources available for a project, the activities that will be carried out to complete a project, and the expected outcomes or results of a project” (Frechtling, 2008). It provides a visual representation in the form of a diagram that shows the flow of the project covering programme components, activities, along with the results to be measured and the expected programme impact. In the simplest terms, “logic models provide a kind of map for a programme or initiative, helping clarify a programme or policy’s destination, the pathways toward the destination, and markers along the way. It provides a simplified picture of the relationships between the programme or policy inputs (resources, strategies, activities) and the desired outcomes of the program” (Andales, 2021).

The key feature of the logic evaluation model employed to facilitate a comprehensive assessment of programme effectiveness includes the illustration of programme development, implementation, and evaluation by using a single flow chart to display the relationship and logical connection among programme components that is, inputs (existing resources), activities (specific initiatives), outputs (programme deliverables), and outcomes (short and long term) (McCoy & Castner, 2020). Two alternatives in addition to these four components are context and impact. The logic model is grounded on the assumption that if resources are sufficient and activities are sound, then the desired short-term and long-term outcomes should be achieved in a logical sequence. This model can be used for varying purposes, including “enhancing communication among programme team members, managing the program, documenting how the programme is intended to

operate, and developing an approach to evaluation and related evaluation questions” (Frechtling, 2008).

Benefits of the logic model to varying constituencies such as programme managers and evaluators, and evaluands that differ in complexity include clarification, communication, management, evaluation planning, the determination of evaluation questions, project documentation, and problem-solving (Schalock, 2001a). These, among others, are the weaknesses and limitations of the logic model: the model may undesirably narrow the range of the programme services; possibility of evaluators taking over the responsibility of programme staff for programme design; an evaluation may be based on a hurriedly developed, inadequate programme theory; it may develop a conflict of interest to defend the evaluation-generated programme theory; it may make the evaluation preoccupied with an apparently endless process of programme theory development; and it may end up creating a theory early in a programme and impede the programme from redefinition and refinement (Andales, 2021).

Owing to the limitations relating to unidentified programme theory, programme services, and programme design noticeable in the original logic model, a study was carried out to transform the original logic model from being a static framework that is less amenable to change into a more dynamic and hence responsive evaluation model. The revised logic model incorporated inputs, activities, outputs, and outcomes, which are the four components in the original model, and added a logic model flow chart, programme theory identification/validation check, and theory research components prior to its use, the use of the Chi-Square test for data analysis, rejection of artificial cut scores, and consideration for contextual influences to the characteristics found in the original model (Frechtling, 2007; McCoy & Castner, 2020).

Tyler's Objectives Model

Tyler's Objectives Model, also known as the Tyler Rationale, is an educational evaluation model developed by Ralph Tyler in the 1940s. The model was primarily used for curriculum design in the field of education and has been adopted in many institutions as a foundation for curriculum design and evaluation. The model is now widely recognized and has been influential in shaping educational evaluation practices. It is commonly used to analyze, interpret, and explain the curriculum and

instructional programme of an educational institution in four simple steps that form the main components of the model: educational objectives, learning experience, organization of learning experience, and evaluation of learning (Tyler, 2002). These four main components are derived from four basic questions that the pioneer of this model expects educators to answer when designing a curriculum and a plan of instruction. The questions are: “What education objectives are the students to be helped to attain? What learning experiences can be provided that will enable the students to attain the objectives? How will the learning experiences be organized to maximize their cumulative effect? How will the effectiveness of the programme be evaluated?” (Tyler, 2002).

Tyler’s model is said to be linear in nature, starting from objectives and ending with evaluation. The model is objective-centered, making objectives play a significant role in its implementation. The objectives, which are derived from the learner, contemporary life, and subject specialists, form the basis for the selection and organization of learning experiences, as well as the basis for assessing the curriculum (Ibeh, 2021). The model measured the extent to which educational programs achieve their set goals or objectives. Being objective-based, Tyler's model measures whether the objectives set by policy, program, or project can be achieved or not. In Tyler’s model, an attained goal or objective is an indication of a successful instructional programme whereas an unattained goal or objective is a pointer to an inadequate instructional program. Thus, the model is only applicable to a training programme with clear, stable, and measurable objectives and is most appropriate when the purpose of evaluation is to discover the extent to which a programme achieves its intended outcome (Tyler, 2002). The model requires that goals/objectives are clearly articulated and spelled out in measurable ways to the programme outcome. Tyler’s rationale “provides a clear and succinct description of the programme and as well delineates a process of measuring the degree to which the objectives are attained” (Gonzalez, 2023). Scholars have documented the strengths and weaknesses of this widely used educational evaluation model. Tyler’s objective model is used to develop curriculum by defining objectives for new curricula and assessing the degree to which the objectives are later realized. Since the emphasis is on learning outcomes instead of organizational and teaching inputs, the model can help avoid the

subjectivity of the professional judgment or accreditation approach. Tyler's model mode of evaluation does not apply to costly and disruptive comparisons between experimental and control groups. Notwithstanding, the recognized merits, the model is criticized for the following demerits: Though good at discovering lapses, the model is deficient in the feedback mechanism that can help stakeholders or evaluators solve the identified problems and improve the training program. The model focuses so much on objectives that it makes no connection between evaluation and organization. It is inappropriate for the evaluation of projects or programs with unstable and unclear objectives. Its overemphasis on behavior makes it fail to evaluate objectives. Overemphasis on training outcomes such as education effectiveness and student achievement makes this model overlook evaluation of the teaching and learning process. Its incomplete consideration of context can limit its applicability in diverse educational programs.

Tyler's model is a goal-based or objective-centered evaluation model. A scholar identified seven steps involved in Tyler's objective evaluation model: one, formulation of clear goals; two, classification of objectives; three, formulation of goals based on measurable behavior; four, determination of when goal achievement can be demonstrated; five choice and development of the proper measurement method; six collection of information or data; and seven, analysis of data or information of achievement on the objectives outlined in character being assessed (Ibeh, 2021). Another scholar, however, proposed three basic steps in applying Tyler's objective model. First, specification of the instructional objectives; second, collection of performance data; and third, comparing the performance data with the specified objectives (Tyler, 2002). The model adopts various evaluation techniques, such as tests, observations, and student portfolios, to assess student performance and provide feedback for instructional improvement. In summary, Tyler's objective model places emphasis on the significance of clearly defined objectives, systematic assessment, effective instruction, and ongoing evaluation to ensure meaningful and effective educational experiences for students. It provides a systematic approach to developing educational objectives and aligning them with instructional strategies and assessment methods. It provided a structured approach to curriculum development, ensuring that educational objectives were

clearly defined and guiding the selection and organization of instructional experiences. The model emphasized the importance of aligning curriculum with desired outcomes, promoting student-centered learning, and assessing student progress towards educational goals.

Scriven's Goal-Free Model

This evaluation model is named after Michael Scriven who created it in 1972. The model was invented as a reaction to low-quality evaluation outcomes of educational projects due to the influence of the project goals (Madaus & Stufflebeam, 2000). Scriven, who also experienced this low-quality evaluation because of the overemphasis on goals, chose to create a new model that would be free from the inducement of goals, calling it "Goal-Free Evaluation" (Slack, 1998). The model compensates for inherent weaknesses in a goal-oriented approach by providing an unbiased perspective of ongoing programs (Guba & Lincoln, 1983). In this model, "official or stated programme goals and objectives are withheld or screened from the evaluator" (Stufflebeam, 2001).

Unlike in Tyler's model where goals and objectives are used interchangeably, Scriven makes a distinction between goals and objectives. In Scriven's model, goals are defined as "broad statements of program's purposes or expected outcomes, usually not specific enough to be measured and often concerning long-term rather than short-term expectations" (Garrett, 1998). Objectives, on the other hand, are described as "statements indicating the planned goals or outcomes of a programme or intervention in specific and concrete terms" (Engel & Dyrness, 2000).

Characteristically, the goal-free model is not based on the set goals, objectives, or programme of activities. Its focus is on total outcomes, which include both intended and unintended outcomes of an educational programme (Spiegel, Bruning, & Giddings, 1999). Goal-free evaluation underscores the role of evaluators in the process of seeking the unintended and undesirable consequences of the curriculum as well as the intended ones (Choiriyah, Khuriyah, & Hakiman, 2023). In this model, an evaluator is an unbiased observer who is not influenced by project goals but is tasked with generating needs profiles from those served by the program, utilizing these profiles to evaluate the programme independently of the set goals. Using methods that are qualitative in nature, the evaluator assesses the overall effect of the

program. The programme is considered useful if it has an effect that is responsive to any of the identified needs. The chief goal of this model is to discover the actual effects (expected and unexpected) of the program, which might not align with the stated goals.

Irrespective of the usefulness of Scriven's evaluation model, it is not recommended as a substitute for the goal-based model; rather, it serves as a complement to it (Lee, 2023). The strength of this model lies in the fact that it allows evaluators to maintain a broad focus on the totality of programme outcomes, rather than being limited to the outcomes produced by the programme goals (Stufflebeam, 2003). It is a valuable supplement to the goal-based model and helps to overcome issues that may arise when the implemented programme goals do not truly reflect the needs for the program. Conversely, the model can only be used as a supplement to the goal-based model and lacks an explicit methodology for its implementation (Far & Karimi Moonaghi, 2023).

Conclusion

This critical review of evaluation models for missiological training programs has provided an in-depth examination of the concept of training programme evaluation and its significance in enhancing the effectiveness of missiological training. Through a comprehensive analysis of existing literature and evaluation frameworks, this study has surveyed common evaluation models applicable to missiological training, including Kirkpatrick's Model, Context, Input, Process, and Product (CIPP) Model, Responsive Evaluation Model, Outcome-based Model, Logic Model, Tyler's Objectives Model, and Scriven's Goal-Free Model.

The study has contextualized each evaluation model, highlighting its strengths and limitations, and provided guidance on the appropriate contexts for their application. The findings of this research underscore the importance of adopting a holistic approach to evaluation, one that considers multiple perspectives and metrics to assess training outcomes. The implications of this study are far-reaching, contributing to the development of more effective missiological training programs that equip mission practitioners for cross-cultural engagement and service. By selecting and adapting evaluation models aligned with programme objectives, trainers and educators can enhance the quality and impact of missiological training.

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